

Green Parallelism towards efficient processing and its applications in emerging fields

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Abstract—From the evolution of green computing all the industries, organizations and vendors started trying to produce outcomes those are as eco-friendly as possible. This initiative led to the great acceptance of green computing in all the emerging fields like grid computing, cloud computing, wireless sensor networks, parallel systems etc. In this paper we are going to discuss the concept of green computing along with its evolution, uses and area of acceptability. Initially greenness was being implemented over hardware components but now it is being spreaded in the field of algorithm designs and softwares also. Objective of green softwares and algorithms is to maximize CPU utilization and reducing CPU idle time so that in a fixed span of time CPU can perform more tasks and increased speed will result in lesser use of energy.

Keywords— Green computing, CPU utilization, CPU idle time, parallel systems, infrastructure services.

I. INTRODUCTION

Green computing is the study and practice of environment friendly computing or IT. This can include designing, manufacturing and using of computers, servers, and related devices such as monitors, printers, storage devices, networked devices, parallel devices and communications systems efficiently and effectively with minimum or no impact on the environment^[1].

The U.S. Environmental Protection Agency introduced Energy Star in 1992, which is a voluntary labelling program and its goal is to promote and recognize energy-efficiency in computing devices, climate control equipment, and other technologies. Its impact was adoption of sleep mode among consumer electronics widely. Energy Star served a type of voluntary label given to

computing devices that succeeded in minimizing use of power while maximizing efficiency.^[2]

Parallelism uses energy in such a way that all the systems are running simultaneously and consuming required power. If the processing can be speeded up then processing time will be reduced and lesser energy will be consumed.

II. CHALLENGES IN GREEN COMPUTING

As per the people who are working in the field of IT from last few decades, the concentration was on the efficiency and effectiveness of computing, networked devices, computing peripherals and infrastructure services as well as on their cost and availability.

The infrastructure is now being an issue in the field of IT as it is affecting the environment and the reason is increased requirement of computing in all sectors, cost of power consumed and global warming. That is why IT people are now concentrating on cooling the system, energy consumption and on the area occupied by data centers and computing devices. Therefore it is important for the organizations using IT that processing ability of computers and related devices should be high, infrastructure should be compact, services provided by infrastructure and use of computing and computing resources should be environment friendly.

Major challenges noticed in green computing are –

- i. Power consumption of equipment and their cooling capacity .
- ii. Increased power consumption by data centers and increased cost of power.

- iii. Increased requirements of cooling components those again need energy and hence usage of is increasing exponentially.
- iv. Managing and maintaining the aspects of power consumption of peripherals and devices.
- v. Proper disposal/recycling of IT waste.[3]
- vi. Increasing efficient and speeded computing.
- vii. Green algorithms and software design. [4]

III. APPLICATIONS OF GREEN COMPUTING

While designing components the factors should be taken care those reduce the power consumption when it will be in use. In the same way while designing applications the aspect should be taken care that it should be efficient enough to utilize CPU as much as possible so that it can be faster and hence power consumed by it and idle time of system will be less. CPU utilization is the ratio of use of CPU over its capability and CPU idle time is time when CPU sits idle and does nothing. So objective should be designing such algorithms those utilize CPU as much as possible and reduces idleness of it. Describing the area of application of green computing in the full extent is not possible but we are listing some of the emerging areas as follows:

- i. Cloud computing – The cloud implementing greenness is known as green cloud. IAAS, SAAS and PAAS become more powerful and efficient and require lesser energy.
- ii. Grid computing – When grids implement the concept of greenness then grid computing becomes more faster and consumes lesser power as it is not only about hardware and peripherals but is about softwares as well.
- iii. Parallel systems – The systems connected in parallel work together and perform subtasks or tasks simultaneously use more power at the same time. There are schemes required those will be used to reduce amount of energy consumed by each of the parallel systems.
- iv. Wireless sensor networks – Sensors and nodes connected as the components of

WSN use reduced amount of energy and hence become more eco-friendly.

- v. Operating systems – Computing resources and devices became more and more powerful in last decade. Hence comparative processing schemes and algorithms are also needed therefore operating systems being developed from last few years are being more efficient in order to utilize the CPU as much as possible.
- vi. Computing resources developments – Now a day the computing devices are being manufactured in the way that they use only up to quarter amount of energy. The older devices were using comparatively very high amount of energy but it is decreased dramatically in present.
- vii. Computer networks – Network devices and networking schemes have become more powerful as a large amount of users can interact over the network and larger amount of data can be transmitted in minimized time and by consuming reduced power.
- viii. Artificial intelligence and neural network – Manufacturing and use of green intelligent systems and appliances is widely being adopted. It led an era of power saving technologies.

IV. CONCLUSION

Green computing is the concept being accepted widely in all the emerging fields of IT. Its concern gives eco-friendly computing which has minimum or no impact on environment. As least energy is used, the existing amount of energy can be used to produce maximum outcome. As we discussed one of the best practices of implementation of greenness is parallelism. Lots of tasks are done by parallel systems and requirement of these are energy efficient algorithms designed in such a way that they should use available amount of energy in the best and most efficient way.

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